

STUDYING THE LUNAR SURFACE USING X-RAY FLUORESCENCE. S. Sharma¹, A. Knyazev, S. Leardini, S. M. E. Mangani, S. Naseem, L. Silveri, A. Zino, and F. Arneodo, ¹New York University Abu Dhabi, Saadiyat Island, Abu Dhabi United Arab Emirates, sandhyasharma@nyu.edu

Introduction: We are developing the Lunar X-ray Spectrometer (LXS) which is designed to study the elemental composition of the lunar surface using X-ray Fluorescence (XRF). In XRF, X-rays are directed onto the Moon's surface, causing it to emit secondary, characteristic X-rays that reveal its elemental makeup [1]. Our instrument facilitates in understanding how the regolith interacts with the lunar rovers so that more robust Moon-based technology can be developed.

LXS Model Design: LXS is a light-weight and low-powered instrument weighing less than 300 grams while consuming 5.0 Watts of power. It uses six radioactive isotopes, four Fe-55 and two Cd-109, as its primary X-ray sources instead of X-ray tubes, that introduce extra mass and require more peak power, parameters that are commonly limited in space missions. The energy of characteristic X-rays scale with the atomic number of its origin element. So, the combination of these two isotopes, Fe-55 exciting X-rays from lighter elements while Cd-109 exciting heavier ones, covers a good range of elements of interest in the lunar surface. A silicon drift detector equipped with a light-tight silicon nitride window is able to detect X-rays with energy down to 0.5 keV making oxygen detection possible [2]. The electronics have been tailored to facilitate for the small size of the cylindrical housing of LXS which is about 5.0 cm in height and 6.4 cm in diameter.

LXS Tests: To prepare for the seamless operation of LXS remotely in the lunar surface, several simulation and experimental tests have been conducted so far:

Simulations. Radioactivity simulations are being tested using Geant4 to finalize various parameters of the instrument, such as the distance and angle between the detector and lunar surface [3]. Additionally, multiple tests to analyze resonance frequency, pyrochocs and stiffness are being run along with thermal simulations in COMSOL to study the temperature fluctuations of the detector and electronics to ensure their optimal functionalities.

Experiments. Alongside simulations, experimental tests of LXS in low-vacuum condition have been conducted to test for the structural integrity of the detector, to choose the best detector window that does not absorb low-energy X-rays to enable detection of low-atomic number elements such as oxygen and to ensure that such low-energy X-rays are visible when using radioactive sources over X-ray tubes.

References:

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